

Rethinking Free Will: A Scientific Revolution in Understanding Human Agency

Abstract

The forthcoming book "The Science of Free Will: How Determinism Affects Everything from the Future of AI to Traffic to God to Bees" by Dr. Samir Varma introduces a revolutionary framework for understanding one of humanity's oldest philosophical questions. Through the novel distinction between "Free Will in Theory" (FWIT) and "Free Will in Practice" (FWIP), the work demonstrates how deterministic physical laws simultaneously preclude theoretical free will while guaranteeing its practical existence. The book draws from quantum field theory, computational theory, and complex systems analysis to show how three fundamental limits to prediction - practical constraints, chaos theory, and computational irreducibility - guarantee that free will persists in practice even though all things are determined. This framework provides par excellence insight into consciousness, artificial intelligence development, and moral responsibility. Perhaps most notable is how it seems to imply that if AI systems are sufficiently similar to human brains as computational systems, with enough reality mimicked, they'll develop genuine agency and consciousness regardless of the essentially deterministic nature of the underlying system. Based on fundamental physics, the work has a scientific rigour that covers quantum mechanics, neuroscience, artificial intelligence, and ethics. In promising to fundamentally redefine our conception of the relation between human agency, consciousness, and mind and matter, this groundbreaking synthesis is a work of the highest intellectual significance.

Keywords

Free Will, Determinism, Quantum Field Theory, Consciousness, Artificial Intelligence, Computational Irreducibility, Moral Responsibility, Chaos Theory, Human Agency, Prediction Limits

A Groundbreaking New Framework

In February 2025 a stunningly prescient book will see publication that will forever change the way we view free will and determinism. "The Science of Free Will: How Determinism Affects Everything from the Future of AI to Traffic to God to Bees" by Dr. Samir Varma presents a

compelling new framework that may finally resolve one of humanity's oldest philosophical puzzles.

Having done a lot of reading into this problem [1], I was sceptical of further attempts at solving it. But this work is a real paradigm shift about how we think about free will, consciousness, and human agency.

The book's central insight is the crucial distinction between "Free Will in Theory" (FWIT) and "Free Will in Practice" (FWIP). Contrary to the impossibility of FWIT due to deterministic physical laws, FWIP actually exists, and that very physical law we are discussing FWIT in relation to ensures its inevitability. A deep analysis of quantum field theory, computation theory, and complex systems yields a seemingly paradoxical conclusion.

The physics-based argument is elegant and compelling: Our brains themselves are made up of quantum fields which follow deterministic laws (everything in our universe is). If free will exists in theory, then it cannot be free will. Yet, there are, in their turn, three fundamental limits on prediction: the practical limits, chaos theory, and computational irreducibility, which guarantee that we will always have free will in practise.

Implications for Science and Society

This framework is far from being abstract philosophy. The book explores how this understanding reshapes our view of:

Consciousness and the Brain: We view the brain as computing, based on deterministic physical law, so we can look at consciousness, at decision making - the nature of human experience - from that angle.

Artificial intelligence: Based on the FWIT/FWIP framework, AI systems considered as computational systems of the same type as human brains may develop legitimate agency and consciousness without being non deterministic.

Ethics and Responsibility: Now that we know FWIP is real and, in some sense, meaningful, we can stick to moral responsibility and ethical frameworks even in a universe where everything is deterministic.

The book's scope is breathtaking - spanning the quantum realm to human consciousness, traffic patterns to bee behaviour, artificial intelligence to the nature of God. But it remains scientifically

rigorous all the way through, with philosophical conclusions based on actual well established physics.

The future of Free Will and Artificial Intelligence

One of the most fascinating aspects of "The Science of Free Will" is its exploration of artificial intelligence through the lens of the FWIT/FWIP framework. In compelling fashion, the book argues that as AI grows more complex, it will begin to behave as though it has free will and become increasingly so, while remaining deterministic at its roots - just as humans do.

However, the insight this has for the development of AI is profound. Debates about AI consciousness and agency are typically assumed to require some sort of non deterministic process if we want it to be genuine free will. But if, by our nature, we are a deterministic system but still have meaningful free will in practise, then so too might AI.

The book also tackles a crucial challenge in AI development: the "black box" problem. The complexity of the decision making process in AI systems makes it less transparent, even to its creators. The FWIT/FWIP framework suggests this opacity isn't a bug but a feature - it is a necessary consequence of computational irreducibility, the same phenomenon that gives humans free will in practice.

A New Scientific Understanding

What makes "The Science of Free Will" particularly compelling is its grounding in fundamental physics. Its argument is built from the ground up, rather than grounded in philosophical speculation, beginning with quantum field theory and moving to consciousness and to artificial intelligence.

Most illuminating is the book's treatment of quantum mechanics. The author shows that while some have tried to find room for free will in quantum uncertainty, they cannot do so. FWIP is strengthened by the fact that deterministic evolution of quantum fields reveals how complex, unpredictable behaviour can result from deterministic laws.

This is a major step forward in our understanding of free will, consciousness, and intelligence in general. If you have ever wondered about these fundamental questions from a scientific, philosophical, or practical perspective, you need to read this book.

The book will be available from February 25, 2025, at: <https://www.amazon.co.uk/Science-Free-Will-Determinism-Everything/dp/1803417315>

As someone who has published in this field [1], I can attest that this work breaks new ground in our understanding of free will and determinism. It gives a coherent framework which not only resolves some of the oldest philosophic disputes but also supplies practical insights for the future creation of artificial intelligence and our appreciation of how human consciousness works.

In fact, this is not just another book about free will but a fundamental rethinking of how we understand the concepts of human agency, consciousness, and mind - matter connections. It surely will shape discussions in physics, philosophy, neuroscience, and artificial intelligence for years to come.

Reference

[1] Sarikaya, F. (2024). Free Will and Determinism: From Human Nature to Artificial Intelligence. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13988196>